

A Study of Attitude towards Corporal Punishment among the High School Students

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Abstract

The study was intended to find out the Attitude towards Corporal Punishment among the high school students in Pudukkottai districts, Tamilnadu. Random sampling techniques were used to select sample of 258 high school students. The Mean, Standard Deviation, ‘t’ test and F test statistical techniques have been used in the present study for the analysis of collected data. The result showed that there is no significant difference in Attitude towards Corporal Punishment among the high school students with reference to their Gender, Locality of the student and locality of the school. But there is no significant difference in Attitude towards Corporal Punishment among the high school students with reference to their Gender, Locality of the student and locality of the school.

Keywords: Attitude towards, Corporal Punishment, High school students

Introduction

Reward and punishment are the two sides of the coin of Motivation of students to achieve a higher level of concentration in the class room. In the Gurukula form of education punishment occupied a prominent place than reward. The ancient Gurus were very strict. They made the students obey immediately without any consideration or sympathy towards the feelings of the students. The parents of the past also approved these actions of the Gurus, since they opined that the Gurus punished the students only for their betterment. So it was easy to maintain discipline, impose blind obedience in the process of teaching learning. But the students were under the constant fear of the Gurus. The punishments given to the students were very severe and sometimes beyond imagination. The students were beaten, canned sometimes were made to hang from the branch of a tree under which a bush of thorns of fire was kept. But the Government does not allow any form of physical violence on the students by the Teachers in the class rooms.

Significance of the Study

In the present educational scenario, the application of Corporal Punishment learning in real classroom depends very much on the skills that the Teacher possesses

The teacher must possess or acquire the skills of teaching the students without using the rod in the classroom. The teacher in the present situation under the norms and rule laid by the Department of Education and the Government must try to disprove the maximum “Spare the rod and spoil child”. This is the felt need of Present day teachers. The teachers must take decisions about the ways of acquiring the skills motivate and promote learning among the students without Corporal Punishments. Teachers have to strengthen this type of skills of face to students of this generation in which most of them are the sensitive to punishment in public or in class rooms. Hence the present study has been undertaken to improve the skills of the teacher not taking up Corporal Punishments.

Statement of the Problem

“A Study of Attitude towards Corporal Punishment among the High School Students”

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the high school students have high attitude towards corporal punishment.
2. To find out attitude towards corporal punishment among the basis of Gender, Locality of the Students and Locality of the School.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. The High school Students have high attitude towards corporal punishment.
2. There is no significant difference between the attitude towards corporal punishment among the basis of Gender, Locality of the Students and Locality of the School.

Review of Related Literature

In India, Divya Disha, one of UNICEF’s NGO partners, has organised child rights clubs in schools in Hyderabad, the most recent achievement being the development and signing the Child Rights Charter by 12 schools. This Charter outlines the roles and responsibilities and obligations of schools, teachers, parents and students. Corporal punishment is implicit within the charter and recent information from the NGO has indicated that the clubs will soon take up this issue.

India’s National Policy on Education (1986) proposed abolition of corporal punishment in schools but no legislation has been passed banning it. In 1999, the Delhi High Court admitted a petition by the Parents Forum for Meaningful Education (PFME) challenging the practice of corporal punishment in schools. This followed statements by the Delhi Government in favour of retaining provisions in the Delhi Education Act that provide for certain forms of punishment to students over 14 years of age. In December 2000, in response to public interest litigation, the Delhi High Court struck down provisions of corporal punishment in the Delhi School Education Act (1973) as being inhumane and detrimental to the dignity of children.

Maldives’ law on the Protection of the Rights of the Child (1991) recognises the rights of children and their freedom and dignity and aims to create conditions in which they can develop their full potential and look forward to a full and satisfying adult life. It prohibits the beating of children and the use by parents of severe punishment that may harm the child mentally or physically. The law also states that punishment in schools must not affect the child physically or psychologically. With this background, the state party report to the CRC Committee in 1997 stated that corporal punishment is prohibited in schools.

The Nepal “Children’s Act” (1992) prohibits cruel treatment of children, but it allows parents, family members and teachers to beat a child lightly if it is for the purpose of correcting a behaviour. The Law of Land (Muluki Ain) states that guardians and teachers shall not be held responsible if they grievously hurt a child in the course of education or defense; if the beating results in death they shall be punished with a small fine.

Method Adopted

Survey method is selected for the present study.

Population of the Study

The population for the investigation was the high school students of Pudukkottai.

Sample of the Study

The investigator and associates observed the high school students in Pudukkottai. A total of 258 cases formed the sample through random sampling method and the strata were considered according to the population variables.

Tools Used in this Study

In the present study the investigation selected questionnaire is a tool used to collect data from the selected sample.

Scoring and Consolidation of Data

Scoring of the response sheets were done as per the joining scheme. The score obtained in all questionnaires along with the personal data are consolidated and tabulated on consolidation sheet for the purpose of analysis. Each subject was given a specific number the data concerned with the High School Students was entered in the specific line, following a specific order. Strongly Agree 4 marks, Agree 3 Marks, Disagree 2 Marks, Strongly Disagree 1 Mark.

Validity of the Tool

The Content Validity to select the tool Construction. The sample for the final study is drawn from 6 High School Schools in Pudukkottai District with total 258 High School Students. Stratified random sample procedure.

Reliability of the Tool

In the present study the typical study the typical test-retest method was employed to evaluate the stability of the measurement.

Statistical Techniques Used

The Mean, Standard Deviation, ‘t’ test and “F” test statistical techniques have been used in the present study for the analysis of collected data.

Hypotheses Testing

1. The High school Students have high attitude towards Corporal Punishment.

Table 1

A study of Attitude towards corporal punishment among the High School Students level hypothesis: Mean Scores of attitude towards corporal punishment among the High School Students Level

Score	Number	Mean	S.D
Valid	258	130.85	13.50

The above table shows that the mean score of the high school students is found to be 130.85 which is higher than 50% and hence it is concluded that the attitude towards corporal punishment is high level high school students.

- There is no significant difference between the attitude towards Corporal Punishment among the basis of Gender, Locality of the Students and Locality of the school.

Table 2

Significant difference in Attitude towards corporal punishment among the basis of Gender, Locality of the Student and Locality of the school

Sl. No.	Variables	Categories	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark	
1.	Gender	Male	110	130.69	14.05	1.65	1.96	NS	
		Female	148	131.03	13.13				
2.	Locality of the student	Rural	136	131.82	14.01	1.64		1.96	NS
		Urban	122	129.78	12.88				
3.	Locality of the school	Rural	92	128.35	11.54	1.65			1.96
		Urban	166	132.24	14.32				

Since the calculated value of 't' is less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference in Attitude towards corporal punishment among high school students with reference to their Gender, Locality of the student, Locality of the school.

Hence the null hypotheses 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 are accepted.

Findings of the Study

There is no significant difference between the attitude towards Corporal Punishment among the basis of Gender, Locality of the Students and Locality of the school.

Educational Implication

Education plays a dominant role in all walks of human life. The overarching education goal for UNICEF is to help children to learn and succeed. The Education department must be well equipped with necessary personnel who can study the reasons for child behaviour and teacher reactions. The State Government today imposed a ban on Corporal Punishment of school Students. Corporal Punishment closes the window into the world of education. Instead of imposing Corporal Punishment to the secondary level student, the teacher can play a vital role to modify the behaviour of the students. The development of this capability is an essential part of the Teacher who has to expertise in handling students without Corporal Punishment. He must acquire a thorough knowledge handling the class, attracting the students and enchanting them to listen to him without Punishments or even harsh words. Thus the investigator taken this problem is developing an attitude of awareness, of the skills of teaching a group of differently skilled students in an effective way.

Conclusion

After analyzing all the facts it has to be noted that corporal punishment is not at all applicable in today’s modern world of reform, it tends to bring negativity and make the child resort to violence, the child could possibly use corporal punishment in future date because of his/her past experience. There are many other ways to bring up a child which would produce positive results making a child understand and value human life and dignity making him/or her better individuals and humans. Corporal punishment though may sound like a better alternative and the last resort to inflict punishment but it is highly advisable not to use it either at homes or schools, there are instances to show that it has a far reaching bad effects upon the students because there has been many deaths in the past due to the use of corporal punishment. So, the government should take a strong stand to prevent its use and it should also be wiped off completely from schools.

References

1. Agbenyega, J. S. 2006. Corporal punishment in the schools of Ghana: Does inclusive education suffer? *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 33(3),107-122.
2. Ashton, V. (2001). The relationship between attitudes toward corporal punishment and the perception and reporting of child maltreatment. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 25, 389–399.
3. Bitensky, S. H. (1998). Spare the rod, embrace our humanity: Toward a new legal regime prohibiting corporal punishment of children. *University of Michigan Journal of Law Reform*, 31, 353–474.
4. Brenner, V., & Fox, R.A. (1998). Parental discipline and behavior problems in young children. *Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 159, 251-256.
5. Cryan, J.R. 1995. The banning of corporal punishment. *Dimensions of Early Childhood*, 23(3), 36-37
6. Clark, J. 2004. Against the corporal punishment of children. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 34(3), 363-371.
7. Davis, Phillip W. 1999. Corporal Punishment Cessation. In *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*. Vol 14, Issue 5: 492–510.
8. Durrant, Joan E. 2000. A Generation without Smacking. The impact of Sweden’s ban on physical punishment. London. Save the Children.
9. Duran, J. E. 2000. Trends in youth crime and well-being since the abolition of corporal punishment in Sweden. *Youth and Society*, 31, 437-455.